

NOVEL APPROACHES TO ENHANCE BACHELOR'S DEGREE OF MEDICAL EDUCATION (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *Healthcare professionals require quality training to deliver safe and effective patient care. However, traditional teaching methods often focus narrowly on knowledge and skills, neglecting the connection to real-world clinical practice. To address this, educators are increasingly turning to gamification – the use of game elements in non-game settings – to enhance student learning outcomes.*

This article investigated the effectiveness of gamification in health professions education and explored the theoretical basis for its success. We found that while gamification generally shows positive results, most studies lacked well-defined control groups and did not fully explore the underlying mechanisms. It's crucial to understand how and why gamification works in order to optimize its implementation. The most promising results came from studies combining assessment and conflict/challenge game attributes. This combination seems to improve learning behaviors and attitudes, potentially translating into better learning outcomes. Future research should investigate this link using robust study designs and examine how specific game elements align with different educational goals. I also highlight the importance of experiential learning, where students actively engage in healthcare improvement initiatives within inter-professional teams. This approach, supported by service-learning pedagogies, fosters the development of real-world problem-solving skills that have a tangible impact on patient care.

Keywords: *gamification, health professions education, experiential learning, improvement science, learning outcomes.*

Introduction. There is a global understanding of the need to improve the quality, safety, and value of medical services. Nevertheless, teaching quality and safety to medical care professional students employs pedagogies with a restricted focus on information, skills, and didactic learning that is unrelated to the design and delivery of real patient care(1). To overcome this difficulty, educators are turning to novel approaches such as gamification. Gamification is the use of game elements in non-gaming contexts. Gamification is becoming increasingly popular among health professions instructors as a means of improving student learning outcomes. However, little is understood about the idea of gamification and its potential operating processes. This study concentrated on empirical evidence for the efficacy of gamification techniques, as well as theoretical justifications for using the specific game qualities. We conducted a thorough search of numerous databases, including all empirical research that evaluated the use of game features in health professions education. Of the 5044 publications initially discovered, 44 satisfied the inclusion requirements. Negative impacts from gamification were not recorded. Almost all studies (n = 40) contained evaluation qualities, which were most commonly combined with conflict/challenge attributes (n = 27). Eight research found that this exact combination promoted the utilisation of the learning material, sometimes leading to better learning results. A comparatively modest number of research (n = 7) were conducted to elucidate the mechanisms underlying the utilisation of game qualities. Our findings indicate that gamification can improve

learning outcomes in health professions education, particularly when game features that increase learning behaviours and attitudes towards learning are included. However, most research lacked well-defined control groups and did not use or report theory to explain underlying processes. Future research should elucidate the mechanisms underpinning gamified educational interventions and investigate ideas that could explain the effects of these interventions on learning outcomes using well-defined control groups in a longitudinal study. By doing so, we may expand on current ideas and get a practical and thorough understanding of how to select the correct game elements for the right educational setting and the right sort of student.(2). Three systematic reviews examined the features of effective undergraduate or postgraduate programmes, as well as their impact on patient care results. Working with clinical teams teaches students and trainee doctors more about improvement than didactic classroom sessions do. Students can be a tremendous resource for improving healthcare, but success requires assistance from an interprofessional learning cohort that includes both academic and clinical mentoring. However, finding space for learning about improvement within packed curricula presents considerable obstacles, and there is a lack of clarity regarding which competencies are most important for healthcare students. The Habits of Improvers offers a novel method that allows students and instructors to view development as a way of working rather than a separate curriculum component or 'project'. To implement the Habits of Improvers, pedagogies that allow for co-learning are required, in which teachers, students, doctors, patients, and families learn together how to enhance care. Learning should be iterative, progressing from problem definition to prototype to testing, and then back to a more nuanced knowledge of the problem. We suggest service-learning as a signature pedagogy for healthcare improvement by providing different learning opportunities that are integrated but apparent in the curriculum.(1).

Qualitative research approaches can be just as significant as quantitative ones, especially in medical education, as long as they both aim to improve educational quality. In contrast to the end—that is, achieving the common goals—the means of both approaches to inquiry are distinct. Their differences in means or processes extend beyond data gathering techniques, study designs, or analysis methodologies; they also differ in assumptions about the world, reality, science, and knowledge. These assumptions, whether implicit or explicit, emerge from a researcher's discussion of philosophical beliefs and research paradigms. The researcher's preference for any of the paradigms and assumptions in light of the most common philosophical concepts such as ontology, epistemology, and methodology leads to the selection of one of the dominant research paradigms to follow, such as objectivism/positivism and interpretivism/constructivism. This is widespread practice in the quantitative-qualitative dichotomy of research, ignoring the new blended approach with a pragmatist perspective. Aside from defining the study's methodology, the researcher's comprehensive exposition of philosophical assumptions and paradigms enables readers to easily grasp the conclusions. Many authors from both main traditions neglect to include this critical part of the study in their published publications. In our work, we used an interpretivist/constructivist paradigm and a phenomenological qualitative technique based on Collaizi's descriptive phenomenological analysis, which was tailored to our environment. The study's experience and lessons gained were determined to be worse when shared in a modified and expanded methodological design. As a result, this paper discusses philosophical perspectives, research paradigms, and traditions that lead to the unique qualitative approach from the standpoint of

methodology in our study regarding objective structure clinical examination (OSCE) experience in a medical department(3,4).

Medical education changes are critical for ensuring that healthcare systems can satisfy current and future population demands. In 2010, a Lancet panel advocated for 'a new century of transformational health professional education', with a special emphasis on the needs of low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like Vietnam. This necessitates policymakers and educational leaders developing and implementing unique and innovative ways to the design and delivery of medical education. This analysis examines the present situation of physician training in Vietnam, as well as how advances in medical education curriculum, pedagogy, and technology are transforming undergraduate and graduate medical education. It also looks at the enabling variables, such as unique collaborations and new educational regulations, that fueled and maintained these breakthroughs. Our research focused on the experiences of five public colleges of medicine and pharmacy that are now reforming medical education, as well as a recently created private institution. Research in the field of medical education innovation is required. Future research should investigate the effects of these improvements on medical education and the quality of graduates. Nonetheless, this evaluation seeks to inspire future advances in medical education in Vietnam and other LMICs.(5).

Globalization in medical schooling is a wide concept that appears in a variety of contexts and is rarely offered as an end in itself. In global university rankings, internationalisation is frequently a significant pillar, encouraging attempts to attract more international professors and students and begin more foreign collaborations. However, what challenges does internationalisation address in medical education? Or does it cause more difficulties than it solves? This special issue on solutionism invites us to question the status quo and thoroughly examine the complexities of situations in order to guarantee that suggested actions produce positive and suitable outcomes. We take up this task by focusing on topics of internationalisation in medical education(6).

As patient participation becomes more integrated into the decision-making processes in the education of health-care professions, we must have a deeper knowledge of how choices are made in these institutions. We must also recognize that our most valued solutions may have an awkward fit and unforeseen repercussions if they reach other areas of health care. Finally, we argue for critical approaches not only to patient engagement solutions, but also to understanding issue statements as they are formed, supported, and disrupted via all of this activity.(7).

In the wake of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, it is abundantly clear to all the necessity of studying the pathology and widespread health consequences associated with the virus. However, what is much less clear is the impact of COVID-19 on medical education. Already, faculty and medical students are grappling with the changes that have been made and attempting to consolidate these with their plan of career development. Changes that may seem relatively minor in comparison to the global pandemic have the potential to be drastic turning points in the career progression. As not much is known regarding the long-lasting impact of COVID-19 on medical education, it is therefore also necessary to record and study the full impact of the changes being made. Persistence and adaptability during this time of challenge are attributes that medical students can demonstrate more readily. While every student has a personal story of how COVID-19 has impacted their education, there is no question that the impacts of COVID-19 will be felt on an extensive level. The panic in the community is palpable, and many are confused by how to proceed

in the wake of COVID-19. This is no different for medical students and faculty and the questions that arise regarding medical education and their future careers(8).

The research includes the study and analysis of the implementation of simulation training. The effectiveness of the integration of distance and simulation education. Creation of a center for simulation training and the work done in the process of teaching students. The objective of the study is to provide data on simulation education, on the features and problems of the implementation of simulation education and the main tasks assigned to teachers. Also, the purpose of the study is to determine the features of the organization of the theoretical content and methods of teaching influences of the online course "Simulation Education". Thus, the experience of creating a course in simulation education indicates that the distance teaching format does not always contribute to the achievement of the set goals for the development of practical skills, the formation of competencies related to knowledge and skills in using modern international and legal documents, as well as principles, rules, approaches to solving urgent problems in the field of medicine(9).

Healthcare delivery has become more complicated, particularly with the addition of digital tools and advanced technologies that can further exacerbate existing disparities. New approaches to solve complex, multi-faceted problems are needed. Human-centered design (HCD), also known as design thinking, is an innovative set of methods to develop solutions to these types of issues using collaborative, team based, and empathetic approaches focused on end user experiences. Originally advanced in technology sectors, HCD has garnered growing attention in quality improvement, healthcare redesign, and public health and medical education. During the COVID-19 pandemic, our healthcare organization recognized notable differences in utilization of virtual (video-based) services among specific patient populations. In response, we mobilized, and using HCD, we collectively brainstormed ideas, rapidly developed prototypes, and iteratively adapted solutions to work toward addressing this digital divide and clinic and systems-level struggles with improving and maintaining digital health access. HCD approaches create a cohesive team-based structure that permits the dismantling of organizational hierarchies and departmental silos. Here we share lessons learned on implementing HCD into clinical care settings and how HCD can result in the development of site-specific, patient-centered innovations to address access disparities and to improve digital health equity(10).

The study investigated the use of e-learning for medical education in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). E-learning has the potential to address the lack of medical professionals in these areas by providing affordable access to high-quality education. However, implementing e-learning programs faces challenges related to infrastructure and adoption. The researchers reviewed studies that evaluated these programs, finding that most were small-scale pilots that relied on subjective measures and lacked strong evaluation methods. Despite these limitations, many studies concluded that e-learning was effective. The researchers call for more rigorous evaluations to better understand the strengths and weaknesses of e-learning in LMICs. This will help improve these programs and ultimately address healthcare worker shortages and improve the quality of medical care(11).

The aim of this research is to determine the current state and historical context of continuing medical education (CME) in Korea and to propose a strategy for future CME improvement. The CME in Korea now faces a number of issues that must be resolved, including the suitability of the yearly credits that are mandated, the continuation of basic refresher training,

the dearth of online education, and the assessment and certification of educational establishments. More time for the required credits, the addition of social competency subjects and teaching strategies, enhanced online learning, assessment to raise the standard of CME, and the implementation of a suitable and methodical assessment and accreditation system are some of the suggested solutions. In addition to being mandated by medical legislation, continuing medical education (CME) and continuous professional development (CPD) are professional prerequisites for maintaining autonomy via self-improvement and self-control. It seeks to raise awareness of the high standard of professionalism demanded by the global society. In the end, it safeguards and advances the physical, mental, and social well-being of individuals everywhere, making it a necessary prerequisite. It is imperative to secure the professionalism of physicians in order to change the continuing medical education system in order to meet the worldwide standards of CME/CPD, which guarantee high quality treatment and patient safety. In order to do this, the authors suggest that the CME system in Korea be improved and implemented based on an internal evaluation and benchmarks of globally recognised CME/CPD systems that adhere to international norms(12).

Following the World Health Organization's declaration of COVID-19 as a pandemic on March 11, 2020, the disease's prevalence has sharply grown worldwide. Jordan declared an emergency status on March 19 and a curfew on March 21 in reaction to the COVID-19 incident. On March 15, all educational institutions were shuttered, and all educational activities, including clinical medical education, were put on hold. As a result, in order to continue medical education during the COVID-19 pandemic-related shutdown of educational facilities, distance learning became a novel mode of instruction. Using computer technology to offer training, including technology-supported learning that can be done online, offline, or both, is known as distance education. Prior to this time, Jordanian universities did not view remote learning as a viable educational option. This research is to investigate the state of remote e-learning among medical students during their clinical rotations and to pinpoint potential obstacles, restrictions, sources of pleasure, and viewpoints on this mode of instruction. Of the 652 students who answered the questionnaire, 538 (82.5%) had taken part in online learning during the COVID-19 epidemic at their medical schools. Overall, 26.8% of students expressed satisfaction with medical distance learning; this percentage was much higher for students who had previously completed distance learning coursework at their medical schools and for instructors who actively participated in class, used multimedia, and allotted enough time for their sessions. The primary mode of instruction was the synchronous live streaming of instructional materials, and the biggest issue raised by 69.1% of students was the quality and coverage of online streaming. They came to the conclusion that distant learning is a novel and quickly expanding strategy for undergraduate, graduate, and healthcare practitioners due to advancements in social media and technology. It could be the best way to keep up learning processes under extraordinary and urgent circumstances like the COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding technological, financial, institutional, educator, and student constraints is crucial for the effective adoption of distant learning in medical education, since technical and infrastructural resources have been cited as a key issue for adopting distance learning(13).

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic has necessitated a sudden transition to remote learning in medical schools. We aimed to assess perceptions of remote learning among pre-clinical medical students and subsequently to identify pros and cons of remote learning, as well as uncover gaps to address in ongoing curricular development. Video casted lectures uploaded

in advance, electronic health record and telehealth training for students, and training for teaching faculty to increase technological fluency may be considered to optimize remote learning curricula(14).

Globally, the COVID-19 epidemic has interfered with in-person instruction at medical schools. Students, instructors, support personnel, and administrators have all been impacted by the usage of remote learning as a last resort. This narrative review study looks at the benefits and problems medical schools have when using remote learning to teach fundamental science in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Using particular keywords, such as "COVID-19 pandemic," "preclinical medical education," "online learning," "remote learning," "challenges," and "opportunities," we searched PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar for pertinent publications. Premedical education has faced a number of obstacles as a result of the pandemic, including the discontinuation of in-person instruction, a shortage of cadaveric dissections, and practical and laboratory sessions. However, there have also been several benefits, such as upskilling and reskilling in new technologies, and integrating online learning into the curriculum. Many medical schools have so far been successful in using emergency remote teaching and evaluation in their learning environment. Utilizing technological breakthroughs, the preclinical stage of medical curriculum has effectively implemented the unique culture of "online home learning" during the COVID-19 pandemic. This innovative approach has the potential to sustain teaching and learning in medical education even after the pandemic ends. The present student cohort's training, however, may suffer later in the clinical years as a result of their lack of practical experience during the preclinical years. It is quite likely that the application of emerging technologies in education—such as virtual simulation, telemedicine, and AI for adapted learning—will be essential to the revolutionary shift and post-COVID medical education(15).

Perceived stress, burnout, and poor sleep quality are high among medical students. Interventions designed to target these issues are necessary to promote the health and well-being of medical students. The purpose of this study was twofold: 1) to assess the feasibility of implementing a sunrise alarm clock intervention with medical students and 2) to evaluate the impact of the intervention on perceived stress, burnout scores, and sleep quality. These findings suggest that the two-week sunrise alarm clock protocol with electronic device removal was effective in improving sleep quality and reducing burnout scores, and perceived stress. However, additional research comparing this intervention to a proper control group is needed to draw meaningful conclusions about the effectiveness of this intervention(16).

Closing the diversity gap is critical to ensure equity in medical education and health care quality. Nevertheless, evidence-based strategies and best practices to improve diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) in the biomedical workforce remain poorly understood and underused. To improve the culture of DEI in graduate medical education (GME), in 2020 the Accreditation Council of Graduate Medical Education (ACGME) launched the Barbara Ross-Lee, DO, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Award to recognize exceptional DEI efforts in US residency programs. The findings of this qualitative study suggest that GME programs might adopt strategies of exemplary programs to improve DEI in residency, ensure compliance with accreditation standards, and improve health outcomes for all(17).

Numerous health facilities and institutions of higher learning have had difficulties since the COVID-19 outbreak began. Although authorities in education have made an effort to handle the new circumstances, the human infrastructure was not prepared for this kind of thing. The

purpose of this study is to elucidate the potential and difficulties presented by the COVID-19 pandemic for medical education. In order to make up for the disruption in traditional classroom instruction, medical schools have been forced to transition from traditional classroom instruction to online learning. The swift and wide-ranging modifications in pedagogy and curriculum have implications for medical schools(18).

All aspects of medical education were affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Several challenges were experienced by trainees and programs alike, including economic repercussions of the pandemic; social distancing affecting the delivery of medical education, testing, and interviewing; the surge of patients affecting redeployment of personnel and potential compromises in core training; and the overall impact on the wellness and mental health of trainees and educators. The ability of medical teams and researchers to peer review, conduct clinical research, and keep up with literature was similarly challenged by the rapid growth in peer-reviewed and preprint literature. This article reviews these challenges and shares strategies that institutions, educators, and learners adopted, adapted, and developed to provide quality education during these unprecedented times(19).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming healthcare, and there is a critical need for a nuanced understanding of how AI is reshaping teaching, learning, and educational practice in medical education. This review aimed to map the literature regarding AI applications in medical education, core areas of findings, potential candidates for formal systematic review and gaps for future research. The current literature has been charted(20). The findings underscore the need for ongoing research to explore uncharted areas and address potential risks associated with AI use in medical education. This work serves as a foundational resource for educators, policymakers, and researchers in navigating AI's evolving role in medical education. A framework to support future high utility reporting, the FACETS framework is proposed (21).

The COVID-19 epidemic has made surgical training more difficult since social isolation is now necessary. Consequently, teaching surgical skills using virtual reality (VR) simulation may be beneficial, particularly in settings that need minimal invasiveness. Visual-spatial ability (VSA) may have an impact on how quickly laparoscopic surgical skills are learned. The impact of VSA for surgical rookies on the complexity of various tasks throughout a protracted training period in a VR simulator, however, is not well understood. In order to assess the impact of past VSA and VSA development on surgical trainees' performance in VR simulator training, our study examined these factors. Our research showed that during organised VR simulator training, all trainees—regardless of prior VSA experience—improved their surgical abilities. Enhancement in surgical performance and training advancement were correlated with higher VSA, and this relationship was more pronounced in more difficult simulated activities. Additionally, we showed that there was a favourable correlation—especially in the early stages of training—between the TG's surgical performance and VSA. According to our findings, prior VSA levels were a reliable indicator of surgical outcome(22).

Context Medical education is committed to teaching patient centred communication and empathy. However, quantitative research suggests empathy scores tend to decline as students' progress through medical school. In qualitative terms, there is a need to better understand how students and tutors view the practice and teaching of clinical empathy and the phenomenon of empathic erosion. This study provides insights into empathic erosion in medical school, including the problems of negative role modelling and the limitations of an assessment system that rewards

‘tick-box’ representations of empathy, rather than true acts of compassion. It also identifies factors that should enable the flowering of empathy, such as new pedagogical approaches to resilience and a role for the arts and humanities(23).

Conclusion: This review underscores the promise of gamification and experiential learning approaches in health professions education. However, it also highlights the critical need for well-designed research to determine how these approaches can be optimized. Future studies should employ robust control groups, longitudinal designs, and theoretical frameworks to understand the mechanisms by which game elements and experiential learning enhance student outcomes. A clearer understanding of these mechanisms will guide educators in selecting the most effective pedagogical strategies for specific educational contexts.

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